

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING STRATEGIES OF SELECTED RESTAURANTS IN DAET, CAMARINES NORTE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies in selected restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte. Descriptive-correlational methods were used to analyze data from 28 casual-dining restaurants. The data were collected through face to face, online surveys and interviews. Social media marketing strategies were measure by brand awareness, engagement, reach, and customer relationships. The study found that most of the casual-dining restaurants operate 3 years and below and 10 years and above, have 4-6 employees, 4,001 and above followers in social media and frequently using facebook as advertising platform. Although all social media strategies were extremely effective, casual-dining restaurants may open to changes and trends that generally affects their operation such as investing more on Information Technology (IT) and technological systems to have more attractive social media marketing; Specifically, to ensure improving connection with customers in promoting the brand. The study recommends that restaurants must have social media campaign plan that may serve as a basis to address the hindrance faced by the casual-dining restaurant.

Keywords: *Casual-dining restaurant, social media marketing, brand awareness, engagement, reach, customer relationships, and social media campaigns plan.*

INTRODUCTION

Companies today have more alternatives for using various social media websites and platforms to advertise their goods and services. Social media are used worldwide, it has a huge impact on the advertising section of the business especially to different restaurants. ICT helped to improve livelihoods as well as business performance in some of the poorest areas and regions (Guterres, 2021).

A lot of business owners gain some advantages in using ICT in their business operations that result in improvement of their productivity. As Internet usage has increased globally, digital marketing has become increasingly important for many firms as a means of marketing and advertisement (Yim, 2020).

According to Li, et al (2019), some of the marketing practices of different restaurants are through Twitter, Instagram, Google+, and Facebook. These different social media sites, cater lot of customers because of ease of accessibility and many of the customers prefer also to just check the menu and products by just clicking on the different social media.

According also to the study of different authors, a lot of metrics can be used to gauge the success of social media. These are brand awareness, engagement, reach, and customer relationship. These four (4) are greatly affected using different social media marketing. Brand Awareness is defined by Rastogi (2018) as the degree to which consumers recognize a product or a business, while social media engagement is a technique used by customers to collaborate on posts and profiles on social media (Eckstein, 2021). In a study by Sinekovich (2022), Reach is the total number of users who like, share, and comment on a social media post. Lastly, customer relationship refers to the strategies used to communicate with customers and improve their experience (Johanesova, 2020).

From a global viewpoint, business gains some advantages in using social media in the form of boosting popularity and profitability, increasing social sharing, promoting products, and potential customer engagement (Manalo, 2020).

In the local records, above 34 percent of Filipinos visited the internet every day, while those people who visited once a week more than 45 percent. In addition, an average of 21.5 hours were spent per week by online Filipino users (Gregorio & Gregorio, 2013).

According to the study by Rahman (2018), social media offers SMEs several advantages, including the ability to become more easily searchable and accessible, attract more customers, facilitate communication with online users, give them an advantage over larger brands and other businesses in their same industry, and finally, help them prepare for the future.

With the virtue of the collaboration of Administrative Order No. 1 in 2008 the DTI-DOH-DA, a combined administrative order implementing the E-Commerce Act (Republic Act No. 8792) and the Consumer Act of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 7394) was released by the Department of Trade and Industry, the Department of Health, and the Department of Agriculture. The Administrative Order, also known as Joint DTI-DOH-DA Administrative Order No. 01, it was intended to mandate rules and regulations to protect

customers in acquiring products and services through online transactions. Both local and foreign sellers and retailers who are engaged in online transactions were covered. In connection with the provision stated in the Administrative Order stated above in maintaining fair marketing and advertising practices, sellers, distributors, retailers, suppliers, or manufacturers engaged in e-commerce are mandated to provide clear, accurate, fair, and more accessible data that will help customers with their decision making whether to buy the products and services offered.

While research studies from multiple authors such as Atienza (2019), Munsayac (2019), Habaradas (2022), and Mia (2022) studied social media marketing topics in qualitative and quantitative research, however, relevant research on social media marketing strategies is still lacking in clarity, especially on the setting and conditions under which the study on the various social media tools that are used and the variance in their effectiveness is carried out.

Furthermore, in this study, one of the main hubs of the province of Camarines Norte's economic activity is the Municipality of Daet, which is a town that is expanding quickly. In 2020, Daet is considered the most competitive town in the Philippines in terms of national economic development, based on the level of competition in its local government unit. Through regional competitiveness coordinating committees, the National Competitiveness Council (NCC) Philippines is leading the initiative. Based on information from the Local Government Unit Office and Department of Trade & Industry, there were around 28 casual dining businesses in the municipality as of 2022.

Within the local context, social media marketing issues are a similar problem for casual restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte. This is because certain restaurants in Daet lacked a formal social media marketing strategy. Moreover, some restaurants employ methods that do not align with their present promotional plans.

According to preliminary data collected from some casual-dining restaurant owners, several of them are unsure of the best marketing strategies to use on social media, which results in some unanswered customer queries and overlooked online transactions. Apart from that, there are casual dining restaurants that have bad reputations caused by unresolved comments and feedback from customers on social media platforms. These problems could be addressed following some social media campaign plans. Some social media pages failure is because they just do not know about or do not consider social media marketing management.

Research Questions

This study aimed to describe the effectiveness of Social Media Marketing strategies of selected Casual-dining Restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte in terms of:
 - 1.1 length of business operation;
 - 1.2 number of employees;

- 1.3 length of time when social media marketing was introduced;
 - 1.4 number of followers; and
 - 1.5 social media marketing platform used in business?
2. What is the effectiveness of the Social Media Marketing strategy of a selected restaurant in Daet, Camarines Norte in terms of:
 - 2.1 brand awareness;
 - 2.2 engagement;
 - 2.3 reach; and
 - 2.4 customer relationship?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the social media marketing strategy of a selected restaurant in Daet, Camarines Norte?
4. What are the problems encountered in using the Social Media Marketing of selected restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what marketing strategy may be implemented to improve the social media marketing of selected restaurants?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher of this study utilizes the descriptive-correlational method of research. According to Bhat (2019), descriptive research is a research method that explains the features of the population, or phenomena being studied. Thus, the descriptive research method was used because the study searches for answers about the profile of restaurant in terms of length of business operation, total number of employees involved in the business, length of time when social media marketing was introduced in the business, number of followers and social media marketing platform used in business. Additionally, the study search for answers about the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies in terms of: brand awareness, engagement, reach and customer relationship and the problems encountered in using the different social media marketing of the selected restaurant in Daet, Camarines Norte.

Another method used was correlational research. It is a form of the non-experimental research approach. Every researcher analyses two variables, recognizes and assesses the statistical association among themselves, with no effect from some extraneous variable. The correlation coefficient indicates the strength of the relationship between the two variables (Fleetwood, 2021). Hence, this method is used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the profile of the restaurant and different social media marketing strategies used.

Population, Sample Size, and Sampling Technique

The total population was twenty-eight (28) based on the number of registered casual-dining restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte provided by the Department of Trade and Industry. The proponent was purposively identified and choose the casual-dining restaurant in Daet, Camarines Norte as a target respondent in the study.

Description of the Respondents

The respondents are the casual-dining restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte, and duly registered in the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) in 2023. They are varied in the length of business operation, total number of employees involved in the business, length of time when social media marketing was introduced in the business, number of followers and social media marketing platform used in business. The eligible respondents were the restaurant managers or owners or the marketing staff who handle the social media platforms of the restaurant in Daet, Camarines Norte.

Research Instrument

The primary data collection tool for the research is a researcher-made survey questionnaire. The tool was used to open the way for the data used in the study. The research questionnaires are divided into three (3) sections and differ based on the details required for the analysis. The first part is the profile of the restaurant regarding length of business operation, total number of employees involved in the business, length of time when social media marketing was introduced, total number of followers, and social media marketing platform used in the business. The second part is the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies used in the business such as brand awareness, engagement, reach and customer relationship. The last part was the problems encountered by restaurants in using social media.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher's adviser and members of the thesis advisory committee review the researcher-made survey questionnaire. It is subjected to the requisite checks on the relevance and meaning of the claims to ensure that the data collected is vital to the aims and objectives of the analysis. The researcher-made questionnaire was validated by consulting the expert including the thesis advisory committee. Then, after thorough checking, to know the usability and accuracy of the questionnaire.

A dry run or pilot testing was conducted. A dry run was performed with twenty (20) individuals in Daet, Camarines Norte as respondents. This activity showed the consistency of the queries, factors, and measures inside the questionnaire and it was utilized to identify potential questionnaire mistakes as well as to verify the questionnaire's validity. The said reliability test results showed 0.988 (excellent) using Cronbach's alpha which means that there is an internal consistency in the questionnaire. Afterwards, it was distributed to the respondents.

The researcher gave a request letter to the selected restaurant in Daet, Camarines Norte for the approval to conduct data gathering. Once approved, informed consent was provided along with the survey questionnaire to the respondents. It was collected, tabulated, and analyzed to produce concrete and accurate results. The researcher guaranteed that the data collected was used exclusively for academic purposes and held strictly confidential. The college's ethical protocols in research are strictly followed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data obtained in this study are evaluated and interpreted utilizing some statistical instruments and techniques. The statistical methods of descriptive and correlational statistics were primarily employed in the analysis of quantitative results. It is necessary to specify the variables as well as the usual relationships that developed between and within them to employ descriptive statistics. Correlational techniques are used to demonstrate statistically when and how closely two variables are associated.

In statement of the problem no. 1 The percentage frequency distribution technique was used to determine the profile of the respondents. While in the statement of the problem no. 2, the weighted mean was used to calculate the effects of the following social media strategies to the profile of the respondents. The weighted mean is used to calculate the respondents' answers to distinguish the relative significance of the variables. On the other hand, in statement of the problem no. 3 it was ranked from highest to lowest to determine the top 3 problems encountered in using social media marketing. Lastly, a correlation statistic is used to assess whether there is a significant association between the profile of the restaurant and the different social media marketing strategies used by casual-dining restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte by using Somers' Delta Correlation Coefficient.

RESULTS

Table 1
Profile of the Casual-Dining Restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Length of business operation		(%)
3 years and below	8	29.6
4-6	6	21.4
7-9	6	21.4
10 years and above	8	29.6
Total	28	100
Number of employees		
1-3 employees	1	3.6
4-6	14	50
7 and above	13	46.4
Total	28	100
Number of years when the business was introduced in the social media		
1000 and below	5	17.9
1001-2000	1	3.6
2001-3000	6	21.4

3001-4000	5	17.9
4001 and above	11	39.3
Total	28	100
Social media marketing platform used in the business		
Facebook	18	64.3
Facebook, Tiktok	5	17.9
Facebook, Tiktok, Instagram	4	14.3
Facebook, Tiktok, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, and Others	1	3.6
Total	28	100

Table 2
Level of Effectiveness of Social Media Marketing Strategy along Brand Awareness

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. A captivating graphic design posts in social media make the restaurant's brand stand out.	4.36	EE
2. Consistent updates or posting of menu offers by the restaurant made the brand well known	4.11	VE
3. More like/share/comments give the restaurant an opportunity to found online	4.21	EE
4. Social media posts, makes the customers updated on the latest offer and promotion of the restaurant.	4.39	EE
5. Creating multiple social media platforms gives the restaurant an opportunity to be known better.	4.46	EE
6. Social media is a way for customer to be aware of the product being offered by the business	4.14	VE
7. Good feedback encouraged customers to try new product being offered	4.43	EE
8. Competitive restaurant food and service rates on social media help to establish the restaurant's brand.	4.32	EE
9. Hiring some brand ambassadors helps the restaurant to publicize their dishes and menu.	3.61	VE
10. Creating videos and reels help the restaurants for better brand recognition	4.32	EE
Over-all Weighted Mean	4.24	Extremely Effective

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	Extremely Effective (EE)
3.41-4.20	-	Very Effective (VE)
2.61-3.40	-	Moderately Effective (ME)
1.81-2.60	-	Slightly Effective (SE)
1.00-1.80	-	Not at All Effective (NAE)

Table 3
Level of Effectiveness of Social Media Marketing Strategy along
Social Media Engagement

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. More share and likes encourage more customers to follow the social media page	4.29	EE
2. Posts and Comments can be used to express customers' feedback to the restaurant	4.14	VE
3. Quick responses in social media makes customers more comfortable to make the purchase decision	4.39	EE
4. List of restaurant dishes or services in a Product Information System (PIS) or in the Menu is accessible and engaging	4.21	EE
5. Restaurants can engage with customers in creative ways using the multiple social media sites	4.14	VE
6. Social Media can be used to immediately respond to complaints and misunderstandings between restaurant and customers	4.36	EE
7. Consistent posting in social media is a way to have more followers and subscriber	4.29	EE
8. Tweets/mentions/hashtags boost the customer's transaction count.	4.14	VE
9. Testimonials on social media make customers relate in the context of a real-world setting.	4.39	EE
10. Tagging and mentioning the restaurant engage more customers	4.36	EE
Over-all Weighted Mean	4.27	Extremely Effective

Rating Scale:

- 4.21-5.00 - *Extremely Effective*
- 3.41-4.20 - *Very Effective*
- 2.61-3.40 - *Moderately Effective*
- 1.81-2.60 - *Slightly Effective*
- 1.00-1.80 - *Not at All Effective*

Table 4
Level of Effectiveness of Social Media Marketing Strategy to Reach

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Viral marketing/posts/videos is a way for more likes/comments/share	4.21	EE
2. More views encourage other customers to try the restaurant's dishes	4.21	EE
3. Social media reach consumers (such as tourists) who would have otherwise never heard of the business.	4.29	EE
4. Tagging some friends/relatives in advertisements is easier through social media posts	4.29	EE
5. More likes and reactions attract more customers to try out the services offered by the restaurant	4.39	EE
6. Posting videos, pictures, and reels enables the restaurant to showcase its facilities and amenities	4.39	EE
7. The social media page serves as a guide for tourist customers in searching for different restaurants	4.54	EE
8. Positive ratings and comments after trying menus boost other customers to try out the menu of the restaurant	4.43	EE
9. Consistent social media posting and updates affect the customers 'decision to visit the restaurant	4.25	EE
10. Consistent social media posting and updates attract customers to try the restaurant's menu.	4.36	EE
Over-all Weighted Mean	4.34	EE

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	<i>Extremely Effective</i>
3.41-4.20	-	<i>Very Effective</i>
2.61-3.40	-	<i>Moderately Effective</i>
1.81-2.60	-	<i>Slightly Effective</i>
1.00-1.80	-	<i>Not at All Effective</i>

Table 5
Level of Effectiveness of Social Media Marketing Strategy as to
Customer Relationship

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Frequent and fast responses to the customer's queries build a long-term positive relationship	4.36	EE
2. Social media serve as a channel for fast feedback from customers.	4.29	EE
3. More followers and subscribers increase loyal customers	4.36	EE
4. Shares and tweets connect customers and the restaurants	4.32	EE
5. Good feedback from customers in social media can create loyal customers/patrons	4.43	EE
6. Comments and suggestions serve as a reference to improve future customer experiences	4.46	EE
7. Social media posts boost the customer's transaction count.	4.54	EE
8. Social media ensure that customers stay updated on the latest developments of the business	4.39	EE
9. Consistent posting creates a good connection between the customers and the restaurant	4.36	EE
10. Positive posts and comments serve as a basis for other customers to connect with the restaurants	4.39	EE
. Over-all Weighted Mean	4.39	Extremely Effective

Rating Scale:

4.21-5.00	-	<i>Extremely Effective</i>
3.41-4.20	-	<i>Very Effective</i>
2.61-3.40	-	<i>Moderately Effective</i>
1.81-2.60	-	<i>Slightly Effective</i>
1.00-1.80	-	<i>Not at All Effective</i>

Table 6
Test for Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Restaurants
and the Level of Effectiveness of Social Media Strategies

Profile	Social Media Marketing Strategy							
	Brand Awareness		Social Media Engagement		Reach		Customer Relationship	
	d	p-value	d	p-value	d	p-value	d	p-value
Length of Business Operation	-.034	.827	.147	.335	-.086	.558	-.068	.627
Number of Employees	.287	.076	.344*	.047	.086	.638	.033	.848
Number of Years When the Business was Introduced in the Social Media	.125	.393	.310*	.008	.129	.332	.136	.293
Number of Followers	.323*	.031	.219	.158	.260	.060	.233	.097
Social Media Marketing Platform	.158	.351	-.105	.576	-.206	.238	.139	.394

*Correlation is significant @.05 level

**Correlation is significant @0.01 level

Table 7
Problems Encountered by Restaurants in Using Social Media Marketing

Problems		Frequency	Rank
1.	Social media is being accessed by everyone, so complaints can be publicly revealed.	15	1
2.	Social media can possibly destroy one's image and reputation.	12	4.5
3.	Social media can attract negative users including spammers, scammers, posers, and bashers	13	2.4
4.	Social media can be a way to news jacking/ piracy of ideas.	6	9
5.	Social media can accidentally release confidential/private information	9	8
6.	Social media users are not always presented with a good representation of their opinions, thoughts and expressions.	12	4.5
7.	Social media is a way to spread bad publicity.	11	6
8.	Social media can also lead to unfair negativity, inaccurate information, and undue criticism	13	2.5
9.	Social media can be possibly abused by the tourist and employees in exposing an employer's trade secrets or business proprietary information.	4	10
10.	Social media can spread false information like wildfire.	10	7

Table 8

Proposed Social Media Campaign Plan for Casual-dining Restaurants

Problems encountered	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Implementation	Time Frame	Responsible Agency/person	Expected Output
1. Social media can be accessed by everyone, so complaints can be publicly revealed.	Monitor public complaints and protect business reputation	Quickly respond to the complaint Do not delete or hide comments or posts as they give a bad impression to customers	Designate personnel to answer the complaints as soon as they arrive	Immediate	Restaurant owner Marketer	Complaints can be resolved immediately The customers will be satisfied that their queries are addressed immediately Attract more customers and eliminate negative customer
2. Social media can attract negative users including spammers, posers and bashers.	To control the flow of negative users including spammers, posers, and bashers	Verify and monitor those clients who frequently visit the social media page.	Resolve immediately the problems between owners and negative customers.	Immediate	Restaurant owner Marketer	Attract more customers and eliminate negative customer
3. Social media can also lead to unfair negativity, inaccurate information, and undue criticism	To prevent inaccurate information and undue criticism	Always monitor social media accounts from time to time	Just always post and comment with accurate information and real posts about the products and business	Immediate	Restaurant owner Marketer	It prevents the destruction of business image and reputation
	To boost social media engagement	Always updates the business social media account through posting and comment. Add employees that will strictly monitored in answering queries in social media	Continuous engage the business to the needs of the customers.	Immediate	Restaurant owner Marketer	Strengthen connection between customers and business social media platforms
	To promote the restaurant brand to customers	Use multiple social media platforms	Create multiple social media platforms to widen the customer's brand awareness	Immediate	Restaurant owner Marketer	The restaurant's brand will be known by a lot of customers

DISCUSSION

Profile of the Restaurants

The respondents of this study were the casual-dining restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte, and were described in terms of length of business operation, number of employees, length of time when social media marketing was introduced, number of followers and social media marketing platform used in business. The data are presented in Table 1.

The profile of the casual-dining restaurants in terms of length of business operation shows that out of 28 casual-dining restaurants, 3 years and below and 10 years and above has the higher frequency of 8 and a percentage of 29.6 and those 4-6 and 7-9 years got the lowest frequency of 6 or a percentage of 21.4. In addition, in terms of number of employees fifty percent or 14 out of 28 have 4-6 employees and only 1 or 3.6 percent have 1-3 employees. On the other hand, in terms of number of years when the business was introduced in the social media 7 and above got the highest frequency of 10 or 35.7 percent while 3-4 years got the lowest frequency of 5 or 17.9 percent. In addition, profile in terms of number of followers in the social media out of 28 respondents, 4,001 and above got the highest frequency of 11 or 39.3 percent. Lastly, in the social media marketing platforms used in the business, Facebook got the highest frequency of 18 or 64.3 percent while using multiple social media such as facebook, tiktok, Instagram, youtube, twitter and others got the lowest frequency of 1 or 3.6 percent.

As for the length of business operation, 3 years and below and 10 years and above got the highest frequency. Some of the restaurants were established because of the rapid change and development. It also revealed that within the criteria most of the restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte are still young with below three (3) years in the operation. These restaurants are still in their start-up stage based on the survey conducted. Moreover, they added that they are newcomers to the market and are widening their business experiences to determine how to overcome obstacles and maintain operations. It is parallel with the study of Rao and Shinozaki (2021) which revealed that 59.6 percent of the surveyed MSMEs had been in operation for less than five years, which are young start-ups. Most SMEs are in the early stages of development and have yet to break into the market.

It also revealed that some of the old and well-established restaurants that operate ten (10) years and above also adopt social media as their marketing strategy. This indicates that casual-dining restaurants have surpassed and succor the first three critical years of operation. Those trials and problems helped them to understand the proper strategies that should apply in different problems they encountered. Moreover, they can sustain themselves as fully functioning businesses because of their long period of existence and they have proven the demands for their products or services being offered to customers. They established their reputation and image in the business industry with long years of business operations. This is the reason why most of the casual-dining restaurant in Daet had existed between ten (10) years and above. This was supported by Mackinnon (2019), almost 90.80 percent of the business who reaches ten years and

above survive in a long run and continue the business operation. The study also concluded that most of the business have an average of 6.7 years.

As for the number of employees, restaurants who have four (4) to six (6) employees got fifty (50) percent of the survey. Normally, casual-dining restaurants have four (4) to six (6) employees. According to Escoffer (2022) the ratio of server per table has one server per 4 to 5 tables. Also, casual dining restaurants usually accommodate 25 tables. Based on the results of the conducted survey with the respondents, the existing number of employees are enough to the actual volume of transactions. This number of employees is sufficient to carry on with the daily transactions of the restaurant.

On the other hand, the least frequency along with the number of employees is one to three employees, this was usually the restaurant in which the manager or the owner is the only one who manage the overall business transaction. During the survey some of the respondent who have one to three employees said it was too expensive for them to hire lots of employees, so as a result they do multi-task in order to continuously manage the operation of the business. The findings were parallel to the study of Cammayo and Cammayo (2020) wherein 92.95 percent of their respondents had less employees. It said that some of the businesses lessened their employees to reduce some of the major expenses; therefore, they only employed a small number of employees to cater the business demand.

In the number of years when the Business was introduced in the social media, majority of casual-dining restaurants used social media 7 and above years. Most of the casual-dining restaurants had adapted long time ago the use of social media as their strategy to advertise their business. Given the benefits of social media as the most widely used sources of information in the world, early adaptation of the use of social media as a platform of marketing is greatly beneficial to introduce the brand and products of the restaurant as early as it possible. It was proven on the article social media adoption by Dwivedi et al (2023), "usage and impact in business-to-business (B2B) Context- A state of the art Literature review", B2B companies started using social media as part of their digital transformation. 83 percent of B2B companies who adapt social media as marketing tool in early years in operation has improved their marketing optimization and customer experience.

However, the 3 to 4 years got the least frequency. It indicates that only few casual-dining restaurant were late adapting the social media. Even though they were late or not early using the social media they still manage to used social media as their marketing tools. Based on the journal of Gerrietts (2014), the use and adaptation of social media platforms have gain significance currency in marketing. As the world is constantly changing, adapting in what is trend is necessity, business that get established on the existing social media platforms now will likely benefit in future years.

In terms of followers in social media four thousand (4,000) followers got the highest frequency of 11. It indicates that having a large number of followers in the social media it increases the visibility of a brand or influencer, it allows them to reach a wider audience

(Wille, 2020). It was supported in the study of Kim (2020), based on her study the followers on social media platforms are likely to have significant contributions to brand sales of businesses. She also utilizes brand attachment theory to predict that the follower effect will be larger for niche brand. Lastly, on social networks, following a brand/seller and clicking the “like” button during an online social interaction are support activities that contribute to brand/seller success. Support activities are expressions of endorsement and indications of support in social groups. It also strengthens by the study of Schwehm and Prigge (2022) in which they used the theory of social exchange theory. According to them, this theory explains the relationship between an influencer (business) and social media followers. It claims that individuals in an exchange relationship (e.g., followers of social media) adapt their behavior towards the exchange partner (e.g., business) based on a comparison of the perceived benefits and perceived costs experienced in the exchange. This means that if the social media sites of the business have more followers, it means that more of the followers gain some benefits with these sites. Most of the social media users follow certain social media sites to gain some benefits for an update on the latest offering of the business.

On the other hand, those business who have a 1000 and below number of followers, who gain a least frequency and got 17.9 percent based on the survey conducted. It implies that they not attracting more followers to support their social media platforms and sometimes the posted social media campaign was not attractive. According to published article by Khan (2023), almost 38 percent of social media users said they use social media to follow funny, attractive and eye catchy content. With this report, business needs to adjust their content strategy accordingly to entertain their followers, as well as provide educational content that encourage more followers to follow their social media page.

Lastly, based on the data presented in table 1 Facebook got the highest percentage among all the platforms presented. According to Ravi et al., (2021), since Facebook was launch it has seen excellent growth and is poised to retain its social networking supremacy. With many benefits associated with this platform it is undoubtedly the most popular social media site, it can be used as a useful tool to promote and advertise a business, it helps to promote a brand, market a business or build awareness of a service or a product.

Based also in the survey, only 1 were using more than 4 (Facebook, tiktok, Instagram, youtube and others) social media platform which obtain 3.6 percentage. Creating and using multiple social media platforms will help to promote and be known the brand and product of the business. however, based on the result the casual-dining restaurant in Daet, Camarines Norte they still prefer to use one to two social media. The result of the study was supported in the study conducted by Gruner and Power (2018), they investigated the effectiveness of the use of multiple social media platforms in communications with customers. It was found that widespread activities on linkedin, twitter and youtube have a negative effect on a company’s marketing activity on facebook. Thus, it is more effective for the company to focus on specific social media platform in forming successful inter organizational relationship with customers. However, this was a

case-to-case scenario. Some of the restaurant who successfully used more social media platforms considered it effective because there are some employees who just focusing to handle their social media account, so it is okay for them to used multiple social media.

Level of Effectiveness of the Social Media Marketing Strategy in Selected Restaurant in Daet, Cam. Norte

The following data on the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies on selected restaurant were gathered: Brand awareness, social media engagement, reach and customer relationship. Tables 2 to 5 shows the responses as presented and discussed here.

Brand Awareness. The table 2 shows that the overall weighted mean of the respondents under effectiveness of social media marketing in terms of brand awareness was 4.24 which can be interpreted as extremely effective (EE). Out of 10 indicators under brand awareness all showed an interpretation of extremely effective (EE) except for the indicator 2,6 and 9 in relation to consistent update or posting a menu, social media flatforms and hiring some brand ambassadors to in order to advertise their brand. These indicators were interpreted as very effective (VE). On the other hand, the indicator who got the highest weighted mean amounting to 4.46 and can be interpreted as extremely effective (EE) can be found in indicator number 5. It is about creating multiple social media platforms to better known the brand of the business and the second highest weighted mean under brand awareness was found in the indicator 7 which about the good feedback encouraged customers to try new product being offered. Lastly, the lowest indicator was found in the indicator 9 in which hiring some brand ambassadors helps the restaurant to publicize their dishes and menus which has a weighted mean of 3.61 and interpreted as very effective.

Overall, the results of the survey shows that the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategies in terms of brand awareness was extremely effective. The highest is creating multiple social media platforms gives the restaurants an opportunity to be known better with a weighted mean of 4.46 and interpreted as extremely effective. Respondents shows that social media marketing really effective to boost their brand and popularity, as evidence by the high weighted mean of 4.24 and the interpretation of extremely effective for majority of the indicators.

From the data collected, it shown that it was extremely effective and very convenient to know the brand and products that restaurant offer through multiple social media platforms with the highest weighted mean of 4.46 percent. Using multiple social media account were effective to business to cater different customers. This can help to reach out those customers who are using other social media not just a facebook. It was very common to use as facebook as means of social media marketing however business must use also different social media to cater those people who are not fan of facebook such as twitter, Instagram, and tiktok. It results were supported by Zylyk (2022) marketers

should get comfortable with one social media channel to promote brand. Business should use different account to fulfill different purposes. Social media demographics greatly vary, so using multiple social media platforms helps the business to accommodate bigger population.

In addition, hiring some brand ambassadors helps the restaurant to publicize their dishes and menu found very effective (EE) by the respondents with the weighted mean of 3.61. It was interpreted that most of the casual-dining restaurant see that some brand ambassadors help their business to publicize their brand for customers to be familiar with the business also through the popularity of brand ambassadors more of the customers attracted and encourage to try out the products and services that they advertise. Brand ambassador also serve as a good model to encourage customers to come and try those products offered by different stores. Ambassadors' serve as their promoting agent to advertise their products and services. It was supported in the report by Castillo (2023) in Restaurant Social Media Statistics and Trends in 2023, it shows that 63 percent of consumers are attracted to try out some menus of the restaurant because of the vlogs and videos of different vloggers. It shows that majority of the customers are using social media to search for a restaurant with the reviews of different vloggers or brand ambassadors. Even though it is the lowest weighted mean, still it shows that a lot of respondents have considered it very effective because some of them still willing to hire some content creator to advertise their business. Still, some restaurants are still allocating some budgets to hire or make a collaboration with different vloggers and content creator and lastly because of the huge influence social media, vloggers were the new advertising agent.

Social Media Engagement. Table 3 shows the data on the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategies in terms of social media engagement. The overall weighted mean under engagement is 4.27 that can be interpreted as extremely effective (EE). Out of 10 indicators, 7 were interpreted as extremely effective (EE) and only 3 was interpreted as very effective (VE), these were the indicators found in indicators 2, 5 and 8 which got the lowest weighted mean of 4.14. The indicators are all about posts, comments, tweets, mentions, and hashtags boost the customer transaction count. While the indicator in number 3 with the highest weighted mean of 4.39 is about quick responses in social media makes customers more comfortable to make the purchase decision. It has interpretation of extremely effective (EE).

The data that were gathered and analyzed indicate that in terms of social media engagement social media helps the restaurant to be aware of what should be focus/target to boost social media engagement. Quick response in social media and testimonial makes customers and restaurants more engaged in social media. Results show that the quick response in social media makes customers more comfortable to make the purchase decision. It was found that this indicator is extremely effective social media marketing strategy along with engagement. As the social media is becoming a platform for customer concerns, reviews, and complaints. Quickly responding to a customer issue shows them

that business is watching and listening. More importantly, a quick response shows that the business care. It resolves things before they escalate on public platform. It was supported in the study of Istanbulluoglu (2017), in which it stated, customers are expected to reply to their complaints within 1 to 3 hours on twitter and within 3 to 6 hours on Facebook. The analysis reveals that both quicker first response and a quicker conclusive response led to a higher satisfaction with complaint handling.

Also, testimonials on social media make customers related in the context of real-world setting found to be extremely effective in social media engagement. Testimonial advertising is effective because it changes the speaker of the advertisement. Instead of the brand, it is the customers who promote the product and service to other customers. This makes the recommendation more authentic and more intimate. Based on the article of local Consumer Review Survey 2025, it found that nearly 50 percent of customer trust customer reviews as much as recommendation from their relatives review and it also found that 62 percent of the customers found a negative testimony, so as it was negative the business should make sure that it will address immediately and just maintain a positive testimonial advertisement. The testimonial should be authentic and unique.

In addition, restaurants can engage with customers in creative ways using the multiple social media sites was found very effective, this implies that more social media sites, the more the restaurants engage to their customers. According to the study of Jha and Verma (2023), the results of their study indicate a stark difference in the way that users respond to the post in two platforms. Facebook-based users do not appreciate relevant messaging in the firm's posts; they appreciate it less than other generic posts of the business, while twitter-based users actively encourage firms and engage more with relevant posts. This finding means twitter and Facebook user groups form differentiated segments within the "social media users" stakeholder group. We can conclude that applying multiple social media sites in business is effective to engage with customers in creative ways. Using also multiple social media platforms we can cater different personality and preferences of the customers.

Lastly, it was found that tweets/mentions/hashtags boost the customer transaction count. Using these three activities in social media help the people follow trending themes on social media platforms. This online tool empowers user to find the information they're most interested in and discover new ideas and activities. According to Wentley (2023) Tweets, mentions, and hashtags can be integrated into successful digital marketing campaigns for companies of all sizes. When this three integrated in social media marketing, business can leverage major social trends for the company's benefit.

Reach. **Table 4** shows the data on the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategy in terms of reach. The overall weighted mean under reach is 4.34 that can be interpreted as extremely effective (EE). Under reach a total of 10 indicators were used to assess the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategies and all these indicators showed an interpretation of extremely effective (EE). Indicator 7 got the

highest weighted mean of 4.54 which interpreted extremely effective and indicators 1 and 2 got the lowest weighted mean of 4.21 which interpreted as extremely effective (EE).

The data that were gathered and analyzed indicate that social media marketing strategy in terms of reach, social media page serves as a guide for tourist customers in searching different restaurants. Social media play a significant role in online tourism as a ubiquitous and popular information source when tourists are searching for destination-related information and for those dishes or restaurants that can be tried or visited by the tourists. Social media serve as a guide for the tourist to search for the restaurants or any establishment that best to visit during their vacation, it really help them to be familiar to the unique dishes and menu that best to the location. This serve as a guide or a map to tourist to find a good and delicious restaurants that serve a delicious menu. This was supported in the study of Liu et. al (2019), based on their study, people made decisions about restaurants both before and during the trip, especially first-time travelers looked at information about local and dining options from various social media sites such as facebook, twitter, instagram and so forth. They usually based their final choices of restaurant and dishes on the reviews, comment and posts in the social media page of the restaurant.

On the other hand, indicator 1 which is Viral marketing/posts/videos is a way for more likes/comments/share and 2 which is More views encourage other customers to try the restaurant's dishes got the lowest weighted mean of 4.21 which interpreted as extremely effective. More Views, viral posts, and videos is a way to encourage customers to try the restaurant's dishes. Once there was likes, views and comment in a social media page, sometimes this was the basis of customers to evaluate if those restaurants are worth to try-on and serve a basis to evaluate if the restaurant are not scammer or if it legit restaurants. This means that that social media page of the business was attractive and more people were interacting to the social media activities posted in the social media page of the business. It was supported in the article of Kim (2013) in his article entitled "They liked and shared: Effects of social media virality metrics on perceptions of message influence and behavioral intentions" based on his mediation analysis indicated that share had an indirect effect on behavioral intentions through the perception of message influence on the self. A significant interaction effect between like and share was also found, such that the presence of high likes increased the third-person perception only when the message had low shares.

Customer Relationship. Table 5 shows the data on the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategy in terms of customer relationship. The overall weighted mean under customer relationship is 4.39 that can be interpreted as extremely effective (EE). Under customer relationship a total of 10 indicators were used to assess the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategy and all of these indicators were interpreted as extremely effective. Indicator number 7 got the highest weighted mean of 4.54 in which social media social media posts boost the customers's transaction count and interpreted as extremely effective while indicator 2 in which social media serve as channel for fast feedback from customers got the least weighted mean of 4.29 which also interpreted as extremely effective. Overall, all the indicators under the effectiveness of social media marketing in customer relationship interpreted as extremely effective.

The data that were gathered and analyzed indicate that in terms of social media marketing strategy in terms of customer relationship social media posts boost the customer's transaction count. The more posts on social media, the more customers can view the page of the business. This claim was supported by the study of Gati et al. (2018), in which he studied 112 salespeople from several industries, his study found that intensive technology use positively affects attitude towards social media, which positively affects social media use. Intensive posts and updates lead to increased customer focus and understanding, and an increased level of customer service. Through posts, it provides firms with a new avenue to connect and converse with their targeted customers in a dialogue fashion and create better customer relationships.

On the other hand, Indicator number 2 which is social media serve as a channel for fast feedback from customers got the lowest weighted mean of 4.29 but it was also interpreted as extremely effective. As the social media is consider as the fastest way or channel to know the comment and feedback of the customers this an effective channel to know better the customers. In the study of Needle (2023), customers who received positive feedback were more likely to show positive emotional states than not receiving any feedback from the business. It shown also in his study the different types of media moderate the relationship between feedback valence and emotional states. More specifically, as compared to private media (e.g., text message) social media plays stronger mediating role.

Test for a Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Restaurants and the Level of Effectiveness of Social Media Marketing Strategy

Table 6 The test for significant relationship that may exist between the profile of the restaurants and the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategies was determined applying the Somers' Delta Correlation Coefficient (d). Table 6 shows that the social media marketing strategy in terms of brand awareness did not obtain any significant relationship along the profile of the restaurants except on number of followers ($d = .399$, $p\text{-value} = .031$) at 0.05 significant level. On the other hand, the social media marketing strategy in terms of social media engagement obtained significant relationship along number of employees ($d = .344$, $p\text{-value} = 0.047$) at 0.05 significant level and the period during which the restaurants started using the social media for marketing ($d = .310$, $p\text{-value} = .008$) at 0.01 significant level. Lastly, the level of social media marketing strategy in terms of reach and customer relationship did not obtain any significant relationship along the profile of the restaurants.

Social media marketing strategy in terms of brand awareness did not obtain any significant relationship along the profile of the restaurants except on number of followers. This indicates that the level of effectiveness of the social media marketing strategy for brand awareness did not show any significant relationship on the number of employees; the length of time that the restaurant has been in the business; the specific period during which the restaurants started using the social media for marketing; and the choice of social media platform (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Tiktok, etc). However, there

was a significant relationship with the number of followers and brand awareness as strategy. This suggests that the number of followers may be considered as a factor in the effectiveness of social media as marketing strategy for brand awareness. It was supported by the study of Dhanesh and Duthler (2019), when the business gains a lot of followers it is easy for the products to be known by other people.

Meanwhile, the social media marketing strategy on social media engagement obtained significant relationship along number of employees ($d=.344$, $p\text{-value}=0.047$) and the period during which the restaurants started using the social media for marketing ($d=.310$, $p\text{-value}=.008$) both at 0.05 significant level. Based on the result, it suggests a moderate positive relationship between the social media engagement and number of employees. In other words, as the number of employees in a restaurant increases, the effectiveness of the social media marketing strategy on social media engagement tends to increase moderately. It was supported by Newberry and Cohen (2021), according to them getting employees involved in social media allows the business to engage in their market through the voices they are most likely to trust. At the same time, it allows employees to showcase their company pride and industry.

Likewise, a moderate positive relationship also exists between social media engagement and period during which the restaurants started using the social media for marketing strategy. In other words, restaurants that adopted social media marketing earlier tend to have moderately better social media engagement. Thus, such profile may be considered as predictors in determining the level of effectiveness of social media marketing strategy in terms engagement. On the other hand, profile along length of business operation, number of followers and the choice of social media platform did not obtain any significant relationship in terms of social media engagement. Hence, these profiles are not considered factors in determining the level of effectiveness of the social media marketing strategy when it comes to engagement. It means that whether a restaurant is a new start up or has been in operation for many years, it does not affect its ability to engage with its audience on social media. Additionally, the number of followers does not affect the social media engagement be it large or few number of followers. Finally, the choice of social media platform does not affect their ability to engage with their audience. It was supported by the study of Dissanayake et al (2019) in which according to them, the widespread global usage of social media has had a tremendous influence on the social interaction between business and customers. When the business early adopts social media as marketing tool, lot of customers will engage with the different activities of the business, aside from that those interaction between the social media accounts of the restaurants and customers will be boost.

Further, the level of social media marketing strategy in terms of reach did not obtain any significant relationship along the profile of the restaurants. It means that the reach on social media as marketing strategy has no significant effect along length of business operation, number of employees, number of years when the business was introduced in the social media, number of followers and the social media marketing platform. These

variables are not considered determinants in the social media marketing strategy along reach. In other words, reaching a wider audience depends on other factors that were not examined in this study.

Finally, the level of effectiveness of social media strategies along customer relationships has no significant relationship along the profile considered. Again, the length of business operation, number of employees, number of years when the business was introduced in social media, number of followers, and the social media marketing platform are not considered factors in determining whether these variables have a significant effect on the customer relationship as a marketing strategy. Hence, the success of social media strategies in building and maintaining customer relationships on social media is not determined by the profile of the restaurants. Similar findings were found in the research conducted by Manalo (2020), which found that the demographics of their respondents were unable to provide a definitive association regarding their respondents' level effectiveness of in social media marketing

Generally, the profile of the restaurants has no significant relationship to the level of effectiveness of the social media strategies except for brand awareness and social media engagement.

Problems Encountered by Restaurants in Using the Social Media Marketing

Table 7. The Table 7 shows the problems encountered by casual-dining restaurants in using the social media marketing. Out of ten indicators in the problems encountered by the restaurants the top three (3) indicators that got the highest frequency are as follows: 1) the social media can be accessed by everyone, so complaints can be publicly revealed, 2) social media can attract negative users including spammers, scammers, poser and bashers and bashers, and 3) social media can also lead to unfair negativity, inaccurate information and undue criticism.

With highest frequency and rank as number 1, the social media can be accessed by everyone. Complaints and unwanted posts can publicly reveal. According to Kala (2023), once information has been leaked into the cyber space, that information is impossible to hold back, and the business can only take responsibility for it. Once it posted, almost everyone will believe in it.

The second problem and third encountered by the business using the social media it can attract negative users including spammers, scammers, posers and bashers and can also lead to unfair negativity inaccurate information and undue criticism. Fake news from the negative users is thus not only harmful to customers, but also to business. It would affect consumers' decision and businesses reputation severely. According to Ordway (2017), numerous high-profile fake review cases have been reported in the news media. Most of the cases involved businesses hiring people to write a fake review for them to promote their products and services.

Proposed Marketing Strategy Plan of the Restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte

Table 8. Based on the result of the study, the top three (3) problems encountered in using social media marketing are as follows: 1) social media can be accessed by everyone, so complaints can be publicly revealed. 2) social media can attract negative users including spammers, scammers, posers and bashers, and 3) social media can also lead to unfair negativity, inaccurate information and undue criticism. The problems mentioned are the top three in which commonly problems that encountered by the casual-dining restaurants to address the challenges that restaurants encountered in using social media marketing, it is recommended that casual-dining restaurants launch a social media campaign plan that would ensure coherent and consistent coordination of the issues. The proposed social media campaign plan, strategies/activities, along with the guidelines on how to implement the recommended solutions that specifically address to promoting brand-awareness, engaging customers with various activities, supervised complaints and prevent destruction of the image, controlling negative users, avoid news jacking, and protect restaurant from data revelation.

The proposed social media campaign plan will be suggested to casual-dining restaurant owners to persuade them to embrace this social media campaign plan, which will help them to avoid some of the problems that may encountered in using social media. This will also help their marketers reach their target audience, use the best tools for running their campaign, and monitor the campaigns' progress consistently. It includes strategies and activities as well as guidelines on how to put the recommended solutions into practice to address the problems that restaurant encounter.

Findings

The following were the study's key results based on the data gathered.

1. In connection with the profile of the respondents, 28 casual-dining restaurants are as follows: in terms of length of business operation 3 years and below and 10 years and above got the highest percentage of 29.6 while 4 to 6 and 7 to 9 got the lowest percentage of 21.4; in terms of number of employees 4 to 6 employees got fifty percentage and only 3.6 percentage in 1 to 3 employees; in number of years when the business was introduced in the social media, 7 and above years got the highest percentage of 35.7 and 3 to 4 years got the lowest percentage of 17.9; in terms of number of followers in the social media most of the respondents have 4,000 and above followers with the percentage of 39.3 and 1,000 to 2,000 followers got the lowest percentage of 3.6 and lastly; in terms of social media marketing platforms used in the business facebook got the highest percentage of 64.3 while multiple social media accounts like facebook, tiktok, Instagram, youtube, twitter and others got the lowest percentage of 3.6.
2. The effectiveness of social media marketing strategy in terms of brand awareness has a weighted mean of 4.24. All ten indicators were rated as extremely effective

except for consistent updates or posting of menu offer; social media is a way for customer to be aware of the product being offered; and hiring some brand ambassadors help the restaurant to publicize their dishes and menu. On the other hand, effectiveness of social media marketing in terms of engagement it gains a weighted mean of 4.27. All ten indicators were rated as extremely effective except for posts and comment can be used to express customers' feedback to the restaurant; restaurants can engage with customers in creative ways using the multiple social media sites; and tweets/mentions/hashtags boost customer transaction count. Under reach, it has a weighted mean of 4.34 and all ten indicators were rated as extremely effective. Lastly, effectiveness of social media marketing strategy in terms of customer relationship, it has a weighted mean of 4.39 and all ten indicators were rated as extremely effective.

3. There is no significant relationship between number of employees, the length of time that the restaurant has been in the business, the specific period during which the restaurants started using the social media for marketing, and the choice of social media platform with brand awareness. Nevertheless, brand awareness has a significant relationship on number of employees ($d=.399$, $p\text{-value}=.031$). On the other hand, in terms of social media engagement there is no significant relationship between length of business operation, number of followers, and the choice of social media platform; but along number of employees ($d=.344$, $p\text{-value}=0.047$) and period during which the restaurants started using the social media for marketing strategy ($d=.310$, $p\text{-value}=.008$) it has significant relationship in terms of social media engagement. In addition, in terms of reach and customer relationship did not obtain any significant relationship along the profile of the restaurants. Again, the length of business operation, number of employees, number of years when the business was introduced in the social media, number of followers and the social media marketing platform are not considered factors in determining whether these variables have significant relationship to the reach and customer relationship as marketing strategies.
4. The top three problems encountered by restaurants in using social media marketing are social media is being accessed by everyone, so complaints can be publicly revealed, social media can attract negative users including spammers, scammers, posers, and bashers, and social media can also lead to unfair negativity, inaccurate information, and undue criticism.
5. The study found that social media campaign plan is important to address the problems encountered by the restaurants when using social media marketing strategies. It will also include strategies, implementation, along with the guidelines on how to implement the recommended solutions that specifically address to promoting brand-awareness, engaging customers with various activities, supervised complaints and prevent destruction of the image, controlling negative

users, avoid news jacking, protect restaurant from data revelation, and take advantage of people trust to social media.

Conclusions

The findings of this study resulted in the following conclusions:

1. The casual-dining restaurants are 3 years and below and 10 years and above operating in business, also have 4 to 6 employees, 7 years and above adoption of use of social media marketing, they also got 4,000 above followers and just only using facebook as social media platform.
2. The level of effectiveness on social media marketing strategies in terms of brand awareness, engagement, reach and customer relationship all have an interpretation of extremely effective (EE).
3. Social media marketing strategies in terms of brand awareness, engagement, reach, and customer relationship are unrelated to the length of business operation and number of followers in social media. The number of employees and several years when the business was introduced in social media affects social media engagement while the social media marketing platform used in the business affects brand awareness.
4. The top three problems encountered in using social media marketing are social media can be easily accessed by everyone, so complaint can publicly reveal, it can attract negative users, and can also lead to unfair negativity, inaccurate information and undue criticism.
5. Based on the findings of the study, the social media campaign plan was developed to address the problems encountered by the restaurants. Also, this plan will help to improve the results in the correlation table.

Recommendations

The researcher developed recommendation based on conclusions, and social media campaign plan:

1. Although, casual-dining restaurants have operating more than a year and already adopt social media marketing a long time ago and have enough employees and followers. Casual-dining restaurants may embrace the use of social media campaigns plan to attract more customers and followers in their social media platforms.

2. Even all of the four variables were all extremely effective, casual-dining restaurants may open to changes and trends that generally affects their operation such as investing more on Information Technology (IT) and technological systems to have more attractive social media marketing; Specifically, to ensure improving connection with customers in promoting the brand.
 3. Casual-dining restaurants may consider other social media marketing strategies that will directly affect the profile in improving and enhancing its marketing activities. Additionally, future researcher may consider other profiles not included in the study, to know if other profiles have significant relationships with the existing factors.
 4. Although casual-dining restaurants have been using effective social media marketing for almost 7 years, casual-dining restaurants may consider those previous solutions made by other researcher to resolve other problems that they may encounter in the future.
 5. An appropriate social media campaign plan was proposed with suggested strategies and implementation for each variable (brand awareness, engagement, reach and customer relationship) that may help solve existing problems encountered faced by the casual-dining restaurants in Daet, Camarines Norte. This social media campaign plan may serve as a basis to address the hindrances faced by the casual-dining restaurants.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to the initiation of the study, the researcher secured explicit informed consent from all participants. Formal request letters were submitted to the relevant restaurant's owners, outlining the study's objectives and the researchers' commitment to ethical conduct. The letters emphasized the protection of participant rights, including data privacy and confidentiality. The researcher committed to conducting the study independently and free from any personal or financial interests that could influence the findings and to maintain strict adherence to academic integrity, ensuring that there was no plagiarism in the study. Upon careful review, the agencies granted their approval, facilitating the researchers' access to the target population. This approval was a crucial step in ensuring the study's legitimacy and ethical compliance.

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